

THE MOTION PROBLEM IN THE USE OF SPATE FOR FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITE SYSTEMS.

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ABSTRACT

An indepth examination of the effects of specimen motion on the technique of thermoelastic stress analysis is presented. It is shown that the presence of a non-uniform temperature distribution, coupled with the material motion due to cyclic loading, can greatly corrupt the measured data. This is particularly important when analysing composite materials in which heat is generated due to viscoelastic processes and/or to internal friction at delamination sites. A series of experiments using delaminated composite specimens as well as an externally heated specimen are presented to illustrate this problem and a mathematical model is developed to account for this phenomenon. By modification of the Spate system the internal heat generation can be measured separately, and thus be used to monitor the damage.

INTRODUCTION

Since the emergence of a practical device (SPATE) for thermoelastic stress analysis some ten years ago, this technique has been exploited extensively for analysing a great variety of isotropic structures (e.g., [1-3]). However, the use of SPATE on composite structures has thus far been limited primarily to simple comparative studies or to qualitative NDT-type applications (e.g., [4,5]). The reason is due largely to a general lack of a thorough understanding on the thermoelastic behaviour of composite materials. It was only recently that a more complete theory on the thermoelastic effect of composite laminates was developed by Wong [6] in which it was shown that inter-laminar heat diffusion must be taken into consideration. In the present investigation, it is shown that internal heat generation, a phenomenon which has real relevance to the testing of composites (particularly at high loads and/or frequencies), coupled with specimen motion due to cyclic loading, poses yet another complication to the analysis of composite structures and must be accounted for in order to avoid mis-interpretation of results.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The severity of this problem was first noticed by Van Hemelrijck, Schillemans et al [e.g. 7,18] during the application of SPATE on a series of fatigue tests on various composite specimens containing a central hole. The material used was of an XAS-914 type carbon fibre composite and the lay-ups considered were $(0^{\circ}_3, 90^{\circ}_4, 0^{\circ})_s$ and $(90^{\circ}_3, 0^{\circ}_4, 90^{\circ})_s$. The specimens were dynamically loaded in a servo-hydraulic MTS testing machine with a sinusoidal waveform at a frequency of 10 Hz and stress amplitudes ranging from 0.2 to 0.5 of the failure stress were considered.

It was noticed that as the load amplitude reached a certain level, the symmetry in the SPATE pattern began to be lost and became increasingly skewed as loading was increased. C-scan inspections of the specimens at the onset of this loss of symmetry invariably showed the onset of delamination around the hole. However, despite the asymmetry in the SPATE scans, the shapes of the delaminated regions were found to be quite symmetrical. This anomaly is clearly illustrated in Figures 1 and 2 showing the SPATE and the corresponding C-scan result for a stress level of 0.5 the failure stress. From Figure 1 it is seen that above the hole there is a higher SPATE signal than expected (the right of the picture) and below the hole there is a lower output than expected (reaching absolute negative values, and thus the term "phase-shift" of 180° referred to in [7,18]).

Figure 1: Spate scan of a $(0^{\circ}_3, 90^{\circ}_4, 0^{\circ})_s$ laminate (dynamic stress = $0.5 \sigma_f$)

Figure 2: C-scans of the specimen corresponding to Figure 1

In Figure 2, a C-scan of the specimen of Figure 1 is shown and clearly indicates the delaminations alongside the hole. It has been common knowledge that an apparent "out of phase" behaviour would occur between the top and bottom edges of the hole. This is commonly referred to as the edge effect and it is the result of the effective variation of emissivity due to the edge moving within SPATE's field of view (Wong [6] showed that SPATE is sensitive to an emissivity change of merely 0.0013%). However, this phenomenon is confined to only a small region near the edges and poses no great problem in practice. The "phase" problem presented here, on the other hand, can be seen to extend over a significant area and can not be ignored.

Figure 3: Schematic drawing of the influence of the static temperature gradient on the Spate result

Nevertheless, the resemblance of these two problems, though remote, does tend to suggest specimen motion to be responsible. Enke [2], although without the benefit of any experimental data nor analysis, postulated that the presence of a high temperature gradient and motion would give rise to "false" SPATE signals. Figure 3 shows the schematic representation of the motion problem when a static temperature distribution is present. Notice the contribution of the temperature gradient in the resulting SPATE signal.

THEORY

To gain a better understanding of this phenomenon, a simplified model of the motion effect will be developed here. Consider a rectangular specimen of uniform cross-section as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Designation of the material axis and the spatial axis

Let the longitudinal material axis of the specimen be x , along which cyclic loading is applied, and the specimen is assumed fixed at the end $x=0$. As a sinusoidal load is applied at the opposite end, every point on the specimen would move relative to a fixed spatial axis y , such that

$$x = y + \delta \sin(\omega t) \quad (1)$$

where ω is the frequency of loading and δ is a small value which is a function of y . As a first approximation, we can assume a linear variation of displacement, viz.,

$$\delta = k y \quad (2)$$

where k would in general be small ($k < 1$).

The general temperature response due to a thermoelastic/plastic loading situation [19] can be represented as:

$$\theta(x) = \theta_1 + \theta_2 + \theta_3 \quad (3)$$

$$= T_1 \sin(\omega t) + T_2 \cos(2\omega t) + T_0 + \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} (a_j \sin(2j\omega t) + b_j \cos(2j\omega t))$$

θ_1 represents the basic thermoelastic temperature (Thomson [10]), θ_2 the mean stress effect explained in detail in Wong et al [11,12] and Jones et al [13] and θ_3 is due to viscoelastic effects and inter-laminar fretting due to damage growth. Using Taylor's series expansion in a fixed spatial axis (Y) we can obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \theta(y) = & \left[T_0 - \frac{k y}{2} \frac{\partial T_1}{\partial x} + \frac{k^2 y^2}{4} \frac{\partial^2 T_0}{\partial x^2} \right] \\ & + \left[T_1 - k y \frac{\partial T_0}{\partial x} \right] \sin(\omega t) \\ & + A \sin(2\omega t) + \left[B + \frac{k y}{2} \frac{\partial T_1}{\partial x} - \frac{k^2 y^2}{4} \frac{\partial^2 T_0}{\partial x^2} \right] \cos(2\omega t) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $A = a_1$ and $B = T_2 + b_1$

To illustrate how motion can affect the thermoelastic data, let us consider two special cases:

a) When internal heating is insignificant. This means that

$$T_0 = A = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad B = T_2 \quad (5)$$

Hence, Eq. 4 becomes

$$\theta(y) = -\frac{ky}{2} \frac{\partial T_1}{\partial x} + T_1 \sin(\omega t) + \left(T_2 + \frac{ky}{2} \frac{\partial T_1}{\partial x} \right) \cos(2\omega t) \quad (6)$$

Inspection of Eq. 6 leads to the following observations:

- i) Motion (non-zero k) gives rise to an apparent steady-state temperature signal whenever the gradient of the fundamental harmonic component is non-vanishing (non-zero $\partial T_1/\partial x$). However, this would not be observed by SPATE as the preamplifier of the SPATE's detector acts to filter out any DC signals.
 - ii) The signal at the fundamental frequency ω contains only T_1 . Since this is indeed the desired signal, it means that the SPATE signal remains unaffected by any motion (excluding of course the edge effect).
 - iii) The 2nd harmonic is affected by motion wherever there is non-uniformity in stresses (i.e., non-zero $\partial T_1/\partial x$). In fact, by taking typical values for a aluminium laboratory specimen containing a circular hole, it has been found [15] that the effect of motion $(ky/2)(\partial T_1/\partial x)$ can be some 4 times greater than the non-linear thermoelastic effect (T_2) near the stress concentrator. This means that any attempt to measure the non-linear effect in a 2-D stress situation (as was noted in the stress decomposition technique of Ryall et al [16]) must take specimen motion into account in order to avoid erroneous results.
- b) Consider now only the fundamental response, as this is the component which is normally measured by SPATE, and suppose that there exists a steady state temperature distribution as a result of internal heat generation so that

$$\theta(y) = \left[T_1 - ky \frac{\partial T_0}{\partial x} \right] \sin(\omega t) \quad (7)$$

It may be seen that for sufficient motion together with an existing steady-state temperature gradient, the term $(ky)(\partial T_0/\partial x)$ can in fact become significant with respect to the actual response of interest T_1 . To illustrate this problem, consider a 0° unidirectional XAS-914 composite in which the physical properties may be taken as in [6], viz., $\alpha_f = 2.8 \times 10^{-6}$, $\rho = 1630 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $C = 935 \text{ J/kg} \cdot ^\circ\text{C}$, and that $T_0 = 300^\circ\text{K}$. It may be shown from equation 7 that a 0.1 mm motion at a location where exists a temperature gradient of 1°C over 10 mm would be sufficient to produce a signal equivalent to approximately 180 MPa. This is indeed severe, and implies that the effects of motion cannot be ignored even when a relatively moderate static temperature gradient is present.

EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

The 3-Hole specimen

To demonstrate that the observed anomaly is due to the motion effect as described above, several experiments were conducted. The first involved the testing of a three-hole specimen as shown in Figure 5. The holes were located in the middle of the width and separated from one another by 10 diameters so that each hole would nominally experience identical stresses, and thus damage behaviour.

Figure 5: Test setup for the three-hole specimen

Line scans were performed through the centre line along the length of the specimen at different load levels. Figure 6 shows the line scan at a dynamic stress of $0.25 \sigma_f$ (peak-to-peak) with the x-axis being the number of scanned points. The locations of the holes can be easily identified by the pairs of opposing "spikes" caused by the edge effect as discussed in [6] and it may be seen that the thermoelastic emissions were reasonably identical around each hole.

Figure 6: Line scan of three-hole specimen for $\sigma_{\max} = 0.3 \sigma_f$ and $\sigma_{\text{dyn}} = 0.25 \sigma_f$

At a stress level of 0.4, the thermal emission from each hole showed a similar "out-of-phase" behaviour as for the single hole specimen (see Figure 7).

Figure 7: Line scan of three-hole specimen for $\sigma_{\max} = 0.5 \sigma_f$ and $\sigma_{\text{dyn}} = 0.4 \sigma_f$

However, for the 3-hole specimen, it is clear that this effect became increasingly large towards the hole nearest the moving grip. This result strongly suggests that specimen motion is a major factor in the cause of this problem.

DAMAGE ASSESSMENT

Under cyclic loading conditions fibre reinforced composite systems show an internal heating which can be used to monitor the damage initiation and evolution [20]. By modification of the SPATE-system, it is possible to measure in a very accurate way, the generated heat within the specimen. This internal heat generation is a consequence of viscoelastic effects and inter-laminar fretting due to damage growth. Figure 8 shows the SPATE scans of a specimen loaded in fatigue at $0.3 \sigma_{failure}$ and a frequency of 10 Hz. The material used was of an XAS-914 type carbon fibre composite and the lay-ups considered was $(90^{\circ}_3, 0^{\circ}_4, 90^{\circ})_S$.

Fig.8 Static temperature field at 78, 387, 509, 597, and 688 10^3 cycles.

CONCLUSIONS

In using the technique of thermoelastic stress analysis on composite laminates, it was discovered that at sufficient load levels, spurious results can occur. The anomalies usually came in the form of a gross loss of symmetry in the thermoelastic data despite symmetrical conditions being maintained. The problem was identified to be associated with specimen motion due to the cyclic loading. A mathematical model of the motion effect was developed and it was shown that even small local oscillations, coupled with the presence of just moderate temperature gradient (as a result of internal heat generation), can produce a significant component which can totally corrupt the stress induced signal. Incidentally, the model also showed that specimen motion has a serious consequence on the measurement of the second harmonic thermoelastic response even when there is no heat dissipation.

A series of tests, using firstly a 3-hole specimen and later an unloaded artificially heated specimen, as well as monitoring the surface temperature gradients of a single hole specimen, were carried out and showed convincingly that motion and temperature gradient were indeed the cause of the problem [19]. Various methods for minimising this problem were considered

and, in the case of symmetrical conditions, a simple technique for eliminating the effects of motion was presented.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to thank A. Vrijdag for producing the illustrations and the Belgian National Science Research Fund (NFWO-FKFO) and the Research Council (OZR) of the Free University of Brussels (VUB) for the support. The authors are also indebted to Drs. A.K. Wong, R. Jones and T.G. Ryall for the many fruitful discussions.

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